

A Descriptive Study for Applying Social Media Platforms in Large Size Companies' Recruitment Process in Jordan

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Abstract

Recruitment is a crucial process which should support the desired developments and strategic achievements for any organization, recruitment landscape has been significantly transformed by advancements in technology, particularly through various social media platforms. This research would investigate largest forty-one companies in Jordan against their recruitment activities over social media platforms in terms of job-vacancy posts, check how this could affect the number of followers for the companies' platforms over social media such as LinkedIn. Also, to investigate if job posts require previous years of in a specific industry or it tends to be open for enable all interested job seekers to apply from various backgrounds with irrelevant industries.

Keywords: Social Media Recruitment, Jordan, Years of Experience.

Introduction

Recruitment is a crucial process which should support the desired developments and strategic achievements for any organization, one of the pillars for a successful recruitment is to have a healthy stream of quality job candidates who enjoy high potentials and capacities to adequately fulfill the job requirements and achieve the desired targets.

Despite of the high unemployment rate which reached 21.5% during the third quarter of 2024 in the Jordanian market as officially recorded by the Jordanian Department of Statistics (Dosweb, 2025), still both recruiters and job seekers could have better chances of jobs matching if technology is effectively utilized by both sides. As the job market becomes increasingly competitive, companies in Jordan are increasingly leveraging social media platforms to enhance their recruitment processes.

In recent years, the landscape of recruitment has undergone a significant transformation, driven by the pervasive influence of social media platforms and technological advancements. As traditional methods such as newspaper advertisements and job fairs become less effective, many companies are turning to social media to reach a broader audience, streamline candidate selection, and foster engagement with potential hires.

Recruitment landscape has been significantly transformed by advancements in technology, particularly through various social media platforms. The integration of platforms like LinkedIn, Facebook, and X (named Twitter before) into recruitment strategies not only facilitates the dissemination of vacancies but also allows for the evaluation of applicants' qualifications and personality through their online presence.

LinkedIn, as an example of a professional networking site, has emerged as a prominent tool for organizations to attract, engage, and hire talent. Also, Facebook and Instagram are also very interactive platforms covering various age groups and maybe all society segments covering all types of discussions, news, advertisements, job opportunities, ...etc.

This research aims to examine the extent to which social media is utilized by the largest companies in Jordan in their recruitment process across different seniority levels (entry, junior, senior, and executive). Moreover, it aims to analyze the effectiveness of social media

platforms such as LinkedIn in attracting candidates based on position seniority through number of interactions and number of followers for companies' relative pages. In addition, to explore if large companies in Jordan requires specific relative field of experience to their industry or service field.

This study is based on a descriptive analysis to understand what is the level of application of social media platforms in recruitment practices by large size companies in the Jordanian market. Moreover, how some of the largest companies in Jordan utilize social media platforms in their recruitment processes against the various seniority levels of the available vacancies on their social media platforms respectively. Building on that, this research should investigate two main hypotheses; (1) to verify if Jordanian companies using social media platforms affect the number of social media effect in terms of the number of followers? (2) to verify if announced vacancies require specific relative field of experience to the announcing company's industry or service field?

Literature Review

Social media platforms have become increasingly important offering new avenues for attracting and engaging potential candidates for various usage directions including social attendance and stories-sharing, business-professional promotions and processes, also political participations. In Jordan, the adoption of social media for recruitment purposes is gaining traction, particularly among younger job seekers. For instance, research indicates that social media has a significant positive impact on political participation among Jordanian youth, suggesting its potential for broader engagement in professional contexts as well (Alodat et al., 2023).

Four main reasons support the growth of social media recruitment as listed by Balasubramanian et al. (2016): (1) full time presence by social media users, (2) easiness for job seekers to check job fit and study the hiring company, (3) high reach for larger size of targeted audience, and (4) a rich medium to share data and excellent range of referrals. Social Media sites such as Facebook, Blog, LinkedIn, MySpace, and Twitter provide a free to use medium, which could be effectively applied to create recruitment opportunities that reach large targeted populations in less time, cost and efforts (Iftikhar & Sadeeq, 2020). In Jordan, MySpace and Blog are not commonly used platforms in comparison to Facebook and Instagram as the most popular social media platforms followed by LinkedIn and X (named Twitter before).

Companies must carefully consider some challenges and factors prior the application of recruitment processes over social media platforms. For instance, companies applying video-enabled material on social media platforms solely to appear trendy, might actually deter applicants from applying (Esch & Mente, 2018). Moreover, factors such as gender differences must be well considered in social media usage (Alodat et al., 2023). Shahid, et al. (2024) stated that social media could give advantage for gender equality across the recruitment process, in which applying recruitment processes over social media platforms could break the traditional barriers for women searching for new jobs.

Social media role is revolutionary and plays an essential part in the entire Human Resources Management (HRM) role beyond e-recruitment to affect also employees' engagement, talent development and employees' retention (Siddik, et al., 2024). Despite that e-recruitment has enabled companies to reach out new pool of job candidates and help them attracting top talents, companies must manage carefully their online presence and potential PR crisis As Generation Z entering the employment market the effect of social media recruitment is proved to have a significant impact on talent acquisition, especially with the most used platforms Facebook and LinkedIn where both play a decisive role in the recruitment process (Meda, 2022).

Despite the various advantages of using social media in recruitment such as cost effectiveness, time advantages, accessibility, and increased exposure; but, several challenges need to be well considered with it including the ethical ambiguity, the homogeneous sampling, and the application of incentives to improve social media recruitment (Jones, et al., 2023).

Research Methodology

This research should analyze the latest job vacancies publicly announced by large size companies in the Jordanian market, where data would be analyzed and checked against the quantity, the seniority level, and the interactions received by job followers on main social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Facebook.

Large size companies were identified through two main funnels: (1) largest size companies by market capitalization announced by CEOWORLD Magazine (2024); (2) large size companies in major industries in the Jordanian market e.g. telecom, banking, automotive, mining, and insurance. Forty-one companies were listed accordingly and subject to following analysis for the aims of this research, listed in Annex (1).

A descriptive research design was employed through extensive analysis of companies pages publicly available on social media platforms specifically LinkedIn. The research starts with searching for social media official pages for each of the forty-one companies on both Facebook and LinkedIn, then for each social media company page all latest (i.e. viewable by a standard social media visitor to the company's page) job posts would be checked and analyzed. Each job post would be analyzed and categorized across different seniority levels, position requirements, and number of interactions by job seekers. Moreover, companies' pages were checked for the number of followers to check its ability to attract job followers in the market.

Data collection was executed over three different intervals (i.e. Jan-25, March 25, and Nov. 25); this aims (1) to avoid same job vacancies or job posts to be counted multiple times, (2) to minimize effect of recruitment seasonality (if exists), and (3) to enable a wider coverage and better understanding of companies' interactions and relative job posts on social media platforms. Captured data was statistically analyzed to reveal the research results and draw the research conclusions using both Jamovi statistical software and Microsoft Excel. Since specific industry year of experience variable is a categorical variable (i.e. Yes, No), Chi Square test is applied to the data to investigate research hypothesis (Gaur & Gaur, 2009).

Research Limitations:

1. Data Collection: data was collected based on social media platforms visibility as a page visitor, some factors could not be viewed accurately such as number of applicants per job vacancy, where if number of applicants is above 100 it shows "+100 Applicants" only.
2. Seniority level might be different considering titles only (e.g. "Senior Analyst" in a Company A might be on a managerial scale vs. a supervisory level in Company B); therefore, in this research the number of past experience years was considered as a revealing factor with vacancy title to indicate position seniority as shown in the below table (1):

Seniority Level	Years of Experience	Examples of Job Titles
Entry Level	0 – 2	Administrative, Drivers, Workers, Fresh Graduate
Junior Level	3 – 4	Officer, Sales Representative, Marketing Officer, Site Engineer
Senior / Manager Level	4 – 12	Supervisor, Section-Head, Department Manager, Senior Analyst

Executive Management	+12	Chief, General Manager, Director, Executive, President, Counselor
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Table 1: Seniority Levels Parameters

- Direct comparison between the various senior levels would not be reflecting any correlation of seniority levels vs utilizing social media in recruitment based on the number of announced vacancies online during the tested intervals. Hence, the limitation is mainly due to the original different proportions of various seniority levels in each company, which follows a pyramid proportion (entry and junior levels are the bottom of the pyramid and senior and executive levels are the top of the pyramid (Drago, 2025) as presented in figure (1) below; higher number of job posts for entry and junior levels in comparison to senior and executive levels does not reflect a higher focus of companies in utilizing social media for specific job levels.

Figure 1: Corporate Pyramid (Drago, 2025)

Key Findings and Practical Implications

The findings of this research were contextualized within existing literature on social media recruitment, with a particular emphasis on LinkedIn's role. The discussion could highlight how the largest companies in Jordan are deploying technology and adapting to the digital recruitment era, and how LinkedIn serves as a bridge connecting them to potential candidates.

In general, large size companies in Jordan have good presence on social media platforms where only three companies (7.3% of companies) were missing on both Facebook and LinkedIn and do not have any official social media presence. Out of the remaining thirty-eight companies' platforms on LinkedIn total of 547 job posts were found and analyzed over the three investigated intervals.

The number of followers for the active companies is noticeable in which approximately 63% of the companies' social media pages are followed by more than 10,000 followers as indicated in figure (2) below.

Figure 2: Categorical Number of followers for Jordanian Companies Social Media Platforms. On the other hand, it was found that recruitment on social media is still not considered well-activated in the Jordanian market were 59% of the researched companies had not posted any job posts or job vacancies on their social media platforms. Reference to the discussed limitations of this research regarding seniority level comparison, the majority of analyzed job vacancies were for junior and entry levels as shown in figure (3).

Figure 3: Job Posts Seniority Level Frequency Chart

Except for Entry level (since no previous experience is expected for this job level) all other vacancy posts were verified and checked against the pre-requisites to have previous experience in specific industry. Chi Square and McNemar Paired tests (tables (2 and 3) were applied in order to answer the hypothesis of this research, it was found that there is a strong

evidence to reject the null hypothesis and accept that there is strong relationship between posted vacancies and requesting candidates to have previous years of experience in specific industry fields.

Contingency Tables					
	Position Seniority				
Specific Industry Experience	Entry	Junior	Senior	Executive	Total
No	158	220	19	0	397
Yes	0	74	70	6	150
Total	158	294	89	6	547

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	Df	P
χ^2	194	3	<.001
N	547		

Table 2: Chi-Square Test

Paired Samples Contingency Tables			
	Specific Industry Experience (Junior and Senior)		
Seniority (J&S)	Yes	No	Total
Junior	74	220	294
Senior	70	19	89
Total	144	239	383

McNemar Test			
	Value	Df	P
χ^2	77.6	1	<.001
N	383		

Table 3: McNemar Paired Test

On the other hand, correlation between number of job posts and number of followers for the companies' pages on LinkedIn test provides enough statistical evidence to have a strong correlation between both variables. This should be well considered as a good indication to expand usage of social media for recruitment activities as audience (i.e. followers) pool is expected to expand accordingly.

Correlation Matrix			
		Total Job Posts	Number of Followers
Total Job Posts	Pearson's r	—	
	Df	—	
	p-value	—	
Number of Followers	Pearson's r	0.835	—
	Df	36	—
	p-value	<.001	—

Table 4L Correlation Matrix Number of Followers vs Number of Job Posts

Conclusion

This research revealed that social media is yet underutilized as an effective recruitment tool by large size companies in the Jordanian market. Moreover, the level of public-interactions by job seekers is found to be limited reflecting an area for potential improvement by recruitment departments. It was also generally noted that no mentioning of compensation level, payment scheme, or any other benefits in the public job posts on LinkedIn, this should be studied and relatively compared by other markets and its effects on higher candidates' interactions and better potential fit for the job post.

Despite the limitations of the data both hypotheses could be verified and answered in this research, where it was concluded that correlation between number of job posts and number of followers of companies' pages on LinkedIn is evident. Also, it was found that there is an evident proof that Jordanian companies do request candidates to have previous years of experience in a specific industry.

In conclusion this research shed light on the current practices of utilizing LinkedIn for recruitment among Jordan's largest companies, focusing on how these practices differ by position seniority. As organizations increasingly rely on digital tools for talent acquisition, the findings of this study could offer valuable insights for improving recruitment processes and strategies, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of hiring within the Jordanian labor market.

Our recommendation for future research is to perform a wider qualitative study where respective recruitment specialists from various human resources departments be interviewed to better understand the limitations and recommendations to apply digital recruitment processes over social media platforms.

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